

COVID 19 AWARENESS AMONG PEOPLE IN INDIA: A SURVEY REPORT

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ABSTRACT

The rapid and extensive spread of the COVID-19 pandemic has become a major cause of concern for the healthcare profession. Given the extensive time needed to conduct a nationally representative household survey and the commonly low response rate of phone surveys, rapid online surveys may be a promising method to assess and track knowledge among the general public during fast-moving infectious disease outbreaks. This study aimed to apply rapid online surveying to determine knowledge of coronavirus disease (COVID-19) among the general public in the India.

KEYWORDS: Rapid online survey, Covid-19, Knowledge, pandemic, public health.

INTRODUCTION

India braces for the COVID-19 pandemic; healthcare professionals on the frontlines are particularly vulnerable to this infection. The virus that causes COVID -19 was initially called as 2019-nCoV and was then termed as syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) by the International Committee on Taxonomy of Viruses (ICTV). It is a new strain which was not found previously in humans has been discovered in 2019.

Previously, the severe acute respiratory syndrome-coronavirus (SARS-CoV) and the Middle East respiratory syndrome-coronavirus (MERS-CoV) have been known to affect humans. Outbreaks of respiratory disease caused by these viruses seem to have originated in animals before moving into other hosts like humans. MERS-CoV was found to be transmitted from Arabian camels to humans, whereas SARS-CoV was transmitted from civet cats to humans. SARS-CoV-2 seems to have originated from bats and first reports of cases were from Wuhan, Hubei Province in China, suggesting an animal-to-person spread from a live animal market. The virus then spread outside Hubei and subsequently, to the rest of the world via human transmission. Several countries have now reported community spread. The World Health Organization (WHO) declared coronavirus disease as a pandemic on March 11, 2020.

With this mode of transmission, healthcare workers are among the highest risk of being infected. The highly contagious SARS-CoV-2 virus is an additional hazard for the healthcare system apart from the burden of extended work hours, physical and psychological stress,

burnout, and fatigue. The objective of this study is to assess the awareness of COVID-19 disease among people in the Indian health care scenario. This was an online based questionnaire-based survey adapted.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The survey was prepared in the form of an online form and was sent to potential responders who included general people and students from India. The period of the survey was May 15 to 30th 2020, and a total of 76 responders completed the survey.

Informed Consent was obtained by all participants in this study. A total of 76 responders from India completed a questionnaire-based survey on the awareness, knowledge, and infection control practices related to COVID-19 infection. Convenient sampling method was used for data collection and the distribution of responses was presented as frequencies and percentages. Descriptive statistics were performed for all groups and subgroups based on the percentage of correct responses.

The self-administered questionnaire consisting of socio-demographic questions, and questions based on knowledge to test participants' knowledge related to covid -19 pandemic and infection control practices related to COVID-19 disease.

Sub-groups were classified on the basis of age (>20 years, 21-30 years, 31-40 years, 41-50 years, 51-60 years and >61 years), Educational qualification and profession (students, Educational sector, Health Professionals and others professionals from the other field). Data were

tabulated in excel, and descriptive statistics were performed using SPSS 17.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A total of 76 people from India responded to the survey. The majority of the responders were from the age group of >20 years (40.8%), Approximately 64.5% of the

responders were students and 13.2 % of the responders were health care professionals. Among the various sub-groups educational wise 50% of the people were found graduates, only 47.4% of the people were having adequate knowledge and 18.4% people were having inadequate knowledge related to covid -19 who completed the survey.

Table 1: Frequency and Percentage of People according to their Age N=76.

Frequency	Percent	Cumulative	
		Valid Percent	Percent
>20	40.8	40.8	40.8
31	31.6	31.6	72.4
21-30	11.8	11.8	84.2
31-40	11.8	11.8	96.1
41-50	2.6	2.6	98.7
51-60	1.3	1.3	100.0
Total	100.0	100.0	

Table 2: Frequency and Percentage of People according to their Profession N=76.

Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Student	49	64.5	64.5
Educational sector	8	10.5	75.0
Health professional	10	13.2	88.2
Others	9	11.8	100.0
Total	76	100.0	

Table 3: Frequency and Percentage of People according to their Educational Qualification N=76.

Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative
10th	2	2.6	2.6
12th	15	19.7	22.4
Graduation	38	50.0	72.4
PG	21	27.6	100.0
Total	76	100.0	

Table 4: Frequency and Percentage of Knowledge Score among people related to Covid -19 N=76.

Frequency	Percent	Cumulative	
		Valid Percent	Percent
Inadequate	14	18.4	18.4
Adequate	36	47.4	65.8
Good knowledge	26	34.2	100.0
Total	76	100.0	

CONCLUSION

There is a need for regular educational interventions and training programs on infection control practices for COVID-19 across all the people. The findings from this online survey could guide information campaigns by public health authorities, clinicians, and the media. More broadly, rapid online surveys could be an important tool in tracking the public's knowledge and misperceptions during rapidly moving infectious disease outbreaks.

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